

Measurement of Basic Material and Processing Properties Affecting Injection-Pultrusion Technology

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ABSTRACT

The pultrusion process has long been used as a technique for producing low cost commercial composite material products. In recent years, aerospace manufacturers have recognized the potential of pultrusion for reducing acquisition costs of their products, and have begun to seriously investigate the possibility of pultruding aircraft and missile structures. The production of high performance pultruded structures requires a detailed understanding of the parameters affecting the quality of the final product. One important consideration in the pultrusion of high quality parts is the wet-out behavior of raw materials. Injection-pultrusion, a modern variation on the traditional wet bath approach to resin impregnation, requires a good understanding of the dynamics of wetting-out reinforcing material with resin. This paper will present analytical methods for predicting the in-plane and transverse resin flow in random mat and 0/90 cloth, and compare the predictions with experimental data.

Another important consideration in pultrusion processing is the compression pressure generated inside the pultrusion die. ACT has developed a technique for measuring the internal distribution of pressure along the interior length of a pultrusion die using a low profile, disposable pressure sensor. Details of this measurement process, as well as measurements made during pultrusion processing experiments, will be presented.

KEYWORDS: Pultrusion, Resin Flow/Permeability/Impregnation, Disposable Pressure Sensor, Compressibility of Fiber/Compaction Force

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently there has been growing interest in the development and refinement of composite material processing methods capable of significantly reducing the acquisition cost of high quality advanced composite hardware. Today both commercial and military composite structures require the use of low cost design methods and manufacturing processes to minimize acquisition and life cycle costs. One process which appears to offer the potential for simultaneously meeting both the cost and performance objectives necessary to accelerate the use of commercial composite materials is pultrusion.

Most pultrusion systems apply resin to reinforcing materials by pulling them through a resin bath prior to the combination entering a curing die. A modern variation of the traditional wet-bath pultrusion process is resin injection-pultrusion. Fanucci et al. (1-2) have been actively involved in attempting to extend the applicability of the injection-pultrusion process to more complex composite structures and resin systems. Some of the earliest investigations of injection-pultrusion were conducted in the early 1960's by J. D. Koppernaes, A. Strommen, and D. Vrke in Norway, at the J. D. Koppernaes Engineering Company (3). However, injection-pultrusion did not progress much beyond applications using simple laminates until recently. Systematic scientific investigation has overcome some of the technical complications associated with resin injection-pultrusion and material wet-out. Injection-pultrusion differs from the wet-bath approach in that matrix materials are injected directly into the pultrusion die, using techniques that are quite similar to those employed in commercial resin transfer molding. One important difference between RTM and injection-pultrusion is that RTM produces one part at a time, while pultrusion makes parts continuously.

A typical pultrusion machine using the injection-pultrusion method is illustrated in Figure 1. The process differs from the wet-bath system in the fiber forming and curing die regions. Matrix materials are injected into the die under high pressure to ensure uniform wetting and low void content. As in wet-bath pultrusion, the material cures and the part exits the die in a cured condition, at production rates similar to wet-bath pultrusion.

Figure 1. Typical Injection-Pultrusion System.

A schematic of a typical resin injection-pultrusion die is shown in Figure 2. This figure illustrates the fiber, mat and optional core material being fed into the die on the left. Resin from a mixing device (not pictured) is injected through ports located at several locations around the die. The injection ports must be properly located in order to achieve complete wetting of the dry reinforcing materials. Good fiber wetting is a critical factor for quality products. Another important consideration in the design of resin-injection tooling is resin backflow out of the entrance to the die. The opening must be properly sized to apply sufficient compression to the fiber to provide a seal, but not so much pressure that pulling loads become unacceptably high.

Figure 2. Typical Injection-Pultrusion Die.

Direct resin injection offers a number of significant advantages over wet-bath methods. When using the wet-bath technique, some residual resin stays in the bath for extended periods of time. It is difficult to maintain consistent properties when fresh resin is mixed with the older, partially cured matrix material already in the bath. It would be desirable to pre-heat resin to lower its viscosity for improved wet-out. This is not usually practical with wet-bath pultrusion because heating reduces the pot life of the resin. Injection-pultrusion solves both these problems. In the injection-pultrusion process the time between resin mixing and curing can be very short, so in-line pre-heating of the resin to reduce its viscosity is possible. Pre-heating the resin results in better impregnation of the reinforcing fibers. The resin can be mixed on-line in the exact amount needed to match the pulling speed of the product. Therefore, control of resin chemistry is much more consistent, and very short pot life resins can be used. Because tooling stays clean, it is possible to change resins simply by switching between resin pumping systems without stopping the process. The closed resin delivery system offers little opportunity for release of volatiles. Therefore, the injection-pultrusion process has a number of quality, health and safety advantages over wet-bath technique.

This paper presents some techniques used by American Composite Technology to analyze resin flow through fiber reinforcements, and predicts compressibility

behavior of materials during the injection-pultrusion process. These techniques and the associated material data can be applied to a wide range of tooling design and material processing situations in addition to injection-pultrusion.

3. RESIN FLOW STUDY

One of the important steps in pultrusion processing is resin wet-out of reinforcing materials. Without complete wet-out, parts will have an unacceptably high void content. Resin flow through the fiber reinforcements is governed by Darcy's law for anisotropic media. The equation is

$$\frac{Q}{A} = v = \frac{k \nabla P}{\mu} \quad (1)$$

where Q = volumetric flow rate (cm^3/sec), A = cross-sectional area of mold, v is the superficial fluid velocity, k is the permeability tensor of the porous medium, μ is the fluid viscosity and ∇P is the pressure gradient driving the flow. The units of permeability are length squared, although the unit "darcy" is commonly reported ($1 \text{ darcy} = 9.87 \times 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^2$).

Many permeability models have been developed based on an approximation of the inter-fiber pore structure described in terms of the average fiber diameter, D_f , and the fiber volume fraction, V_f . Among them, conduit flow models are the most appropriate, of which the best known is the Carman-Kozeny model. The Carman-Kozeny equation is

$$k = \frac{D_f^2}{16C} \frac{(1 - V_f)^3}{V_f^2} \quad (2)$$

where C is the Kozeny constant accounting for tortuosity and pore nonuniformity. The predictive capability of the permeability models are severely limited. Because idealized structures are assumed and the models depend only on the fiber diameter and fiber volume fraction, they are strictly applicable only to uniform or narrow distributions of fiber volume. In real cases, it is possible for fiber reinforcements to have similar fiber diameters and porosities yet markedly different permeabilities.

For aligned fiber reinforcements, there are two principal flow directions. One is flow in the fiber direction and the other is flow perpendicular to the fiber direction (transverse direction). Theoretically, when the fibers are perfectly aligned, permeability through the fiber direction will never reach zero with increasing fiber volume fraction because the maximum packing ratio of circular cross section fibers occurs at fiber volume less than 1, leaving long continuous channels in the flow direction. However, transverse direction permeability will reach zero when the fiber volume fraction (V_f) reaches the maximum possible fiber volume fraction (V_m). The flow direction will affect permeability tremendously. In-plane flow behavior of random mat and 0/90 cloth will be between the two extreme cases. The permeability will be very dependent on

porosity and fiber orientation, which in turn are related to compressibility behavior. The empirical equation based on the compressibility study (4) is;

$$k = \alpha (B * V_m - V_f)^4$$

$$V_f < V_m \text{ and } 1 \leq B \leq 1/V_m \quad (3)$$

where α is the fitting constant, and B is the fiber orientation constant. Constant B is related to the resin flow pattern and is affected by fiber orientation and pore structure. If fibers in the layers are more aligned to the flow direction, flow patterns are straight. In this case, B will be closer to $1/V_m$. As fibers are laid more perpendicular to flow direction, B will be closer to 1. In the random mat, flow paths are very convoluted. Therefore, permeability will approach zero when V_f reaches V_m . In the 0/90 cloth case, the flow path is less constricted so B will be higher than 1.

Experiments were conducted using specially designed fixtures (Figure 3). In-plane and transverse permeabilities were measured with different materials as a function of fiber volume fraction. Materials used in the flow tests are;

- 1) 0/90 Cloth - BGF Industries, Inc. (Style 64T) - for in-plane testing
- 2) 0/90 Cloth - Bean Glass Fiber, Inc. (Style 3) - for transverse testing
- 3) Random mat (Quasi-isotropic) - PPG Industries Inc. (0.3-0.4 Kg/m²)

Two types of oil were used as the fluids in the experiment. Corn oil was used for the in-plane experiment. Motor oil was used for the transverse experiment. Viscosities measured using a Brookfield viscometer were 55 and 375 centipoise at 22°C. Both oils exhibited Newtonian behavior at shear rates between 37.5 and 750 s⁻¹. Details of experimental procedures are described in Reference 5.

Figure 4 shows the in-plane and transverse flow results, and compares the data with theory. Fitting constants are shown in Table 1. The data fits very well with this empirical model. Maximum measured volume fraction for random mat and 0/90 cloth are 0.60 and 0.68. These data were collected in a related study at compression pressures of 1200 psi on the samples (4). It can be seen that permeability is closely related to fiber compressibility. 0/90 cloth shows higher permeability than random mat at the same fiber volume fraction.

Table 1. Curve Fitting Constants for Empirical Flow Model.

		A	B
In-Plane Flow	random mat	23310.70	1.00
	0/90 cloth	6440.70	1.25
Transverse Flow	random mat	3324.61	1.00
	0/90 cloth	1190.85	1.25

Figure 3. Experimental Set-Up for Measuring Permeability.

Figure 4. Effect of Fiber Orientation on In-Plane and Transverse Permeability.

4. COMPRESSIBILITY STUDY

During composite processing, a compaction force is applied to the fiber reinforcements to obtain the desired fiber/resin ratio in the finished product. Without careful monitoring and control of the compression profile of the composite during processing, the ability to produce high quality parts is severely reduced. Knowledge of the relationship between compaction force and fiber volume is of interest to all composite processors. Compression force versus sample thickness was measured using a specially designed fixture fitted in an Instron tensile/compression tester. Sample thickness and compression force

Figure 6. Schematic of Disposable Pressure Transducer.

Figure 7. Typical Pressure Vs. Resistance Curve.

TABLE 2. Typical Disposable Pressure Sensor Specifications.

PARAMETER	VALUE
Size	5/8" x 7/8" (15.8 x 22.2 mm)
Gage Area	7/16" diameter circle (11.1 mm)
Thickness	0.012" (.31 mm)
Repeatability	
Cycle-to-cycle	±2%
Part-to-part	±15%
Optimum Pressure Range	1 to 200 psi (7 to 1400 KPa)*
Frequency Response	0-1000 Hz
Temperature Range	-25 to 800 °F (-30 to 425 °C)
Max Current	5 mA/in ² (1 mA/cm ²)
EMI	Insensitive to EMI

*Special calibration permits measurement of pressures above 1,500 psi.

Experiments were conducted using a disposable sensor and thermocouple to measure the compression pressure and temperature generated inside the pultrusion die. Figure 8 illustrates a typical pressure profile measured with a disposable pressure sensor. Forces acting normal to the die surfaces are generated both by compression of the reinforcing fibers and pressurization of the matrix materials. Thermal expansion during heating competes with volumetric shrinkage of the resin as it cures to produce "peaks and valleys" in the pressure profile.

A technique to measure the compression pressure as a continuous function of fiber volume fraction using the disposable sensor was developed. This equipment was designed to allow the measurement of the dynamic consolidation response of dry reinforcing material as it was pulled through a tapered die (Figure 9). The die was designed with a 0.1 inch thick inlet and had a linear taper to a 0.06 inch thick outlet. Die length was 12 inches. 7 layers of the cloth were pulled from spools, through the wider die inlet and out the narrower

were recorded on a strip chart. Figure 5 shows the effect of fiber orientation on compressibility. These results indicate that compressibility is strongly dependent on the fiber orientation.

Figure 5. Effect of Fiber Orientation on Compressibility.

Another technique has been developed to measure the pressure using a disposable pressure sensor during composite processing. The sensor allows pressure distribution data to be generated using techniques similar to those conventionally used to measure temperature with thermocouples. A postage stamp-sized, 0.01 inch thick gage printed on a thermoplastic film forms the basis of this sensor technology.

Although the device illustrated in Figure 6 appears much like a strain gage, its mode of operation is quite different. The sensor is built from two thin layers of material. One layer has an interdigitated grid of electrically conductive ink printed on its surface. This arrangement permits no direct contact between the two patterns, resulting in an open circuit. The other layer has a thin film of pressure sensitive conductive polymer applied to its surface. The two layers are bonded together in a way that causes the conductive resin to bridge the gaps between the interdigitated fingers. The device responds to increasing surface pressure by undergoing large resistance reductions that can be easily and repeatedly correlated to applied force. Figure 7 shows that the resistance is logarithmically proportional to pressure. The gage is extremely sensitive to changes in load at low pressures, and becomes less sensitive as pressure rises. The gage is usually calibrated to 200 psi, but has been used in applications as high as 1,500 psi. Table 2 summarizes some of the primary characteristics of the gage. Like most polymer materials, the conductivity of the sensor is affected by temperature. For this reason active temperature compensation is currently required.

die exit with a roller-puller mechanism. Pulling speed was approximately 6 inches/minute. A disposable pressure sensor was fed into the inlet portion of the die along with the reinforcements. Pressure data was recorded as a function of position using a computerized data acquisition system.

Figure 8. Graphite/Epoxy Part Processed with Pressure Sensor and Thermocouple.

Figure 9. Testing Set-Up for Pressure Measurement in a Tapered Pultrusion Die.

Figure 10 illustrates a typical result of one test. As the graph shows, at low fiber volumes near the die entrance the gap is wide and therefore applies little pressure to the material. As compaction begins, relatively small changes in pressure produce large fiber volume changes. For the particular material used in this test, very little force was needed to raise the fiber volume to about 40%. Above this fiber volume, compaction force increases exponentially with fiber volume. The material finally approaches a maximum attainable fiber volume, which is primarily a function of material orientation and form. At this point small additional increases in fiber volume require very large changes in compaction force.

Figure 10. Pressure Data Using a Disposable Sensor in a Tapered Pultrusion Die.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented testing methods for measuring in-plane and transverse permeability, and compressibility. It was found that permeability and compressibility are inter-related, and are mainly dependent on fiber volume fraction and fiber orientation.

This paper also described the characteristics and application of a new type of pressure sensing device designed specifically for measurement of locally applied pressures in composite material processes. Until this device was developed, no cost-effective method for making many of the processing pressure measurements described in the preceding sections existed. The sensor's small size and thickness permit it to be placed directly at points where pressure information is desired, rather than following the conventional method of inferring pressures from far field measurements. As illustrated in this paper, the sensor is capable of generating processing data for pultrusion, one of the most difficult composite manufacturing techniques to observe directly.

6. REFERENCES

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